

Conditions of Peasantry during Dogra Rule in Kashmir

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Abstract:

In an agricultural society, the vast majority of people worked as peasants. A peasant is an individual of a very uniform and homogeneous group of families that work together to run a small farm or ranch. Irfan Habib defines a peasant as one who engages in agriculture independently, using his own tools and the labor of his family. In Kashmir, where farming and allied industries were vital to the economy, farmers were seen as productive machines whose goods supported a huge urban population, government employees, and artisans. In Kashmir, the general name zamindar (Gruce) for peasant persists to this day. A large majority of Jammu and Kashmir's population (over 80%) resided in rural areas that were involved in agriculture in some way during the time period under review. The presence and interaction of several social groupings within each village made such self-sufficiency feasible. Kashmir's peasantry played a crucial role in shaping the region's traditional village society. Each the village had a dominant zamindar caste, but it's Muslim and non-Muslim residents came from a variety of other castes. In this study, we shall examine the conditions of peasants in Kashmir during Dogra administration.

Keywords: Peasantry, Dogra, Jammu and Kashmir, Rights, Conditions.

Introduction:

Shanin's words provide a full picture of the rural population. The peasantry is made up of people who are involved in subsistence farming. To provide for their fundamental necessities and to carry out their obligations to those in positions of political and economic control, they mostly use simple tools and the labor of their families.¹ A special affinity for the land, the peasant family farm and the peasant village community as basic units of social interaction, a distinct occupational structure, and the effect of historical background and patterns of growth are only some of the seven pillars that make up this notion.

Peasants made about 90% of Kashmir's population and were the main source of tax income for the government. However, they lived in abject poverty and hopelessness during this time period. This phenomenon may be traced back to the feudal structure of the agricultural economy. In this setting, Lawrence paints a picture of life for the peasantry as follows: The peasant's endured excessive labor, insufficient nourishment, verbal and physical abuse, incessant demands, and various forms of minor oppression. As a result, agricultural productivity was pitiful, tax payments were ignored, and peasants resorted to migrating from one village to another in search of rest and break from oppression.²

Jammu and Kashmir's historical story hinges heavily on the years between 1885 and 1953. The agricultural industry, which made up a large share of the state's workforce, is partly responsible for the site's landmark classification because of its historical importance in connection to key institutional shifts within the sector. Therefore, the Dogra Maharajas were tasked with making

economic development a top priority.³ A major agricultural crisis, on the other hand, had far-reaching effects on both urban workers and rural peasants. Despite the best efforts of the British provincial government to modernize agriculture in the 20th century, the agricultural industry continued to be plagued by high taxes, incidents of corruption in government, and administrative negligence. Multiple changes were made to the agricultural policy of the Dogra Maharajas with the primary aim of increasing tax revenue to the government. Given this background, Lieutenant Colonel Torrens Henry D' Oyley made the following insightful observation:

Gulab Singh went farther than his predecessors in establishing excessive taxes and extortion, worsening the country's final situation compared to its starting one. The claim that they levied steep taxes is, in fact, true. One may argue, though, that this particular monarch took advantage of his people much too often. They did not only steal a lot of money from farms, the textile industry, and people's hard work; they also went to tremendous measures to steal money from everywhere they could.⁴

The British Residency was established in the area in 1885, and, with the help of Kashmiri nationalists, likely helped a series of land reforms near the century's close. As a consequence of Dogra's feudal practices, however, agricultural development in Kashmir has lagged well behind that of adjacent Punjab. The British government of India has taken several steps to modernize agriculture in the province of Punjab.⁵

After Dogra authority was established in Kashmir, the local peasants suffered a violation of their Haqi Malikana, or legal property rights.⁶ The

Dogra regime's strategy to protect itself from the potentially hostile but powerless masses involved redistributing the wealth generated by large landholdings among a select group of landlords, including "Jagirdars," "Chakdars," and "maufdars," with "Zanindars" occupying a lower position. Unlike in other parts of the Indian Subcontinent, the word "Zamindar" has a specific meaning in Kashmir. The term "Zamindar" in Kashmiri context refers to farmers who do not pay taxes for the government and may include both landowners and those without land.⁷

Specifically, Lawrence concludes that Muslims farmers have no choice but to grow shali. In addition, the current taxation system is designed in a way that makes their efforts, notwithstanding how hard they work, inadequate to feed themselves till harvest. Not only do these farmers not have legitimate property rights to their land or crops, but they also have no way to really profit from them. Instead, they are seen as little more than the machines that produce shali for a region's mostly idle people.⁸ As a result, the state's need exceeds the farmers' excess output. The trend of rural residents moving from one village to another in quest of better economic prospects is, thus, to be anticipated in a highly productive area.⁹

Inside Kashmir author Prem Nath Bazaz lamented, "The poverty of the Muslim masses is awful." while discussing the plight of Muslim farmers. Rather of looking like someone who is contributing to the riches of the state, a Muslim peasant who is clad in rags that can barely cover his body and is barefoot seems like a hungry beggar. The Muslim farmer spends the whole summer working in the fields to earn enough money to cover state taxes, the official's rasum, and the interest owed to moneylenders. During harvest season, sepoy's were sent to the villages in advance to collect the tax in kind. The process of collecting rent was a heist and a nightmare for everyone involved. Most of them are serfs who are landless labourers for absentee landowners. The money they get from their share of the harvest seldom lasts more than three months. During the colder months, many fled the state to find employment as day laborers in British India's urban centers. The peasant's plight is dire, and many of them die each year without anyone paying attention or singing their praises. "Nobody feels any sympathy with this distressing picture of poverty. The channels through which human compassion and charity can be expressed have been depleted."¹⁰

It cannot be said with any certainty that the rural population of Kashmir lacked social consciousness, as they voiced their discontent with the status quo in their own unique ways and through their own channels, such as when, during the severe

famine in 1877, an anonymous Kashmiri forwarded a memorandum to the viceroy of India in Delhi, containing grave allegations of mismanagement.⁴

During Maharaja Ranbir Singh's 1877 visit to the Achabal hamlet in Kashmir, agrarian resentment became increasingly apparent as peasants for the first time lodged appeals against instances of official highhandedness and corruption. This is evidenced by the fact that revenue agents were forced to reimburse the bribes they had obtained from the peasants.⁴

Farmers in the Kashmir valley at the end of the 19th century reacted negatively to British rule in a number of ways. These included giving up farming, moving to other parts of British India, hiding their harvest, changing careers, holding public demonstrations and processions to various Sufi shrines, and submitting petitions to the British government.⁹

Between 1895 and 1933, the agrarian system in Kashmir underwent significant change, largely due to the appointment of Mr. Plowden as the British Resident in Srinagar and the influence exerted by sympathizers of Kashmiri Muslims from external regions. This change prompted the Dogra Maharaja to enact a number of reforms in the agrarian sector.²

The recommendations put forth by the two settlement officers resulted in significant modifications to the land revenue system in Kashmir. In 1895-1896, peasants were granted the right of occupancy, known as "assami rights," which allowed them to occupy the land as long as they fulfilled their obligation of paying the estimated revenue. However, it was strictly prohibited for them to engage in the sale or mortgage of the property. Evaluating the advantages and disadvantages of granting occupancy rights, it became evident that this measure enhanced the sense of security and belonging among the oppressed peasants, as it minimized the risk of eviction. Consequently, they became more focused on optimizing the utilization of their land. Furthermore, this policy led to the settlement of peasants, fostering the development of communal awareness.² It is crucial to acknowledge that these rights were exclusively granted to Khalsa lands, while peasants working on estates owned by privileged landholders remained precarious tenants, susceptible to expulsion at any time. During this particular phase, the collection of income was conducted in the form of cash rather than in kind, and the rates were duly established, minimizing the likelihood of corrupt practices among the ranks of tax officers. The traditional practice of Gilgit Begar, which had a detrimental impact on the Kashmiri peasantry, underwent transformation following the

construction of the Gilgit Cart Road during the latter half of the 19th century.¹⁰

Despite these positive developments, the most disagreeable and detrimental aspect of this time period was the bestowal of assami rights upon landowners during and after the year 1900 A.D., which solidified their social standing and provided them with increased opportunities for land acquisition, leading to an increase in evictions. The government therefore established the Tenancy Act in 1923 to provide tenants with assured housing.¹¹

Since land revenue was collected in cash, those who did not have a steady source of income, such as peasants, turned to moneylenders, most of whom were Pandits, for loans at extremely high interest rates. The debtor has been making annual partial payments using both monetary currency and non-monetary means, but after a lifetime of such efforts, the modest debt of 30 to 40 rupees remains unpaid.⁷ In addition, because of the deplorable state of the peasantry, landowners were continually on the lookout for a window of opportunity in which the assamis may be granted property rights, which would allow them the right to sale and mortgage.⁴

When Lord Reading, Viceroy of India, arrived in Kashmir in 1924, he was presented with a paper detailing the plight of tenants who had been wrongfully deprived of their land rights.⁸

Peasant movements, such as the All India Congress, the Muslim League, and most notably the Jammu and Kashmir Muslim Conference (renamed the Jammu and Kashmir National Conference in 1939), fought for the rights of Kashmiri peasants and demanded an end to their hardships during the later period (1934–1953), putting the Maharaja under significant pressure to improve their conditions.¹⁰

The Land Alienation Act of 1933 constituted a significant triumph for impoverished farmers, building upon the recommendations put forth by the Glancy Commission in 1932. This legislation imposed limitations on landowners, preventing them from selling more than one-fourth (25%) of their holdings during the initial ten-year period. The primary objective of this measure was to curtail the propensity of peasants to sell off all their land to affluent individuals. The rationale behind this restriction stemmed from concerns that the absence of such safeguards could potentially exacerbate the precarious circumstances faced by peasants.¹¹ Furthermore; the Act reinforced the 1925 State Subject Ordinance, which was subsequently enacted as law in 1927. Consequently, the acquisition of land within the State by non-state subjects became illegal, thereby contributing to the welfare of the disadvantaged peasantry.⁸ In this manner, the Act served to safeguard the rights and interests of the peasants on a broad scale.

The Maharaja implemented the Right of Prior Purchase and Pre-emption Act and the Agriculturalists Relief Act, which had significant positive implications for the peasantry. These measures enabled the peasants or tenants to hold moneylenders (referred to as waddars) accountable through legal means. The court not only gained the authority to regulate the waddars' arbitrary interest rates but also to establish a debt repayment schedule that considered the peasants' capacity to pay. Additionally, the peasants received loans for seeds and agricultural implements, as well as access to advanced fertilizers, with the aim of enhancing agricultural productivity. These initiatives were designed to improve the economic conditions of the peasantry. In 1936, the All Jammu and Kashmir Village Upliftment Association was established to address the economic backwardness of the peasants.¹² Notably, the formation of Cooperative Societies played a crucial role in promoting farmer welfare by providing loans at nominal interest rates.¹³

The administration instituted a policy to reduce the financial burden on the peasant population by doing away with taxes like Nazrana and Malikana altogether. Additionally, land revenue was significantly reduced, going from 38% to 25%, or roughly a quarter of the total agricultural output.¹²

In 1935, the legislature passed the Kar-i-sarkar Bill, which not only outlawed all forms of begging but also specified that the people hired to do this work—known as collies—would be entitled to compensation for their services.¹²

Despite these shifts, the peasantry as a whole persisted despite significant reductions in land and other sources of income, such as the system of landlordism, which persisted until 1947.¹⁴

Sheikh Mohammad Abdullah, a figure revered by his impoverished populace, assumed the responsibility of addressing the issue of exploitative practices facilitated by the existing agrarian system. Upon assuming power in 1948, he initiated the Big Landed Estate Abolition Act (1950) with the objective of empowering peasants by educating them about government measures aimed at granting them ownership of the land they cultivated. This act imposed a limit of 186 kanals (approximately 22/75 acres) and facilitated the redistribution of surplus land among landless laborers and share-croppers without providing compensation to the landlords.¹⁵ Furthermore; it abolished the special privileges enjoyed by mufidars and mukarrar-khwars (recipients of cash grants). Additionally, Sheikh Mohammad Abdullah emphasized the rational reorganization of agriculture by eliminating landlordism, ensuring land ownership for cultivators, promoting the formation of cooperative

groups, and allocating uncultivated land to tillers for cultivation, among other measures.¹⁶

Undoubtedly, the land reforms implemented by Sheikh Abdullah on behalf of the Nationalists constituted a remarkable measure aimed at addressing the enduring poverty prevalent in Kashmir. However, the success of this endeavor cannot be attributed to a single individual or entity, but rather is the result of the efforts of everyone involved.

Conclusion:

Shanin emphasizes the centrality of land, the family farm, and the village community as social components in his peasantry. Kashmir's 90% peasant population relied on simple tools and labor to satisfy their sustenance requirements and complete their political and economic obligations. Feudal agriculture caused tremendous poverty and sorrow.

The traditional Dogra Maharajas pursued land reforms to boost the royal coffers, but Kashmir's agricultural economy stagnated. The Dogra administration stripped Kashmiri peasants of Haqi Malikana, or ownership rights. Muslim peasants were shown as impoverished beggars who worked in the fields to pay taxes. The rural populace of Kashmir protested the current situation in numerous ways. The appointment of Mr. Plowden as the British Resident in Srinagar and the influence of Kashmiri Muslims from outside the province changed Kashmir's agricultural system between 1895 and 1933. The Dogra Maharaja was forced to modernize agriculture when Mr. Andrew Wingate and Sir Walter R. Lawrence were appointed British settlement officials. The Viceroy of India, Lord Reading, submitted a note in 1924 demanding that tenants be granted land rights. The Maharaja implemented agricultural reforms under pressure to improve peasant circumstances. In a nutshell Kashmir's peasantry was complicated and difficult, affecting workers and peasants.

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